

Deliverable 4.3

Results of the European Sounding board work

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Executive Summary

This report offers insights into the work and achieved results of RETHINK's European Sounding Board (ESB henceforward). The ESB helped RETHINK with the project's objective to shape new forms of science communication. This strategic hub worked towards an integrated vision of the new science communication, linking up the emerging learning communities (Rethinkerspaces) and its outcomes to policy alignments. The interdisciplinary Sounding Board, which consists of independent members with diverse backgrounds and areas of expertise, ensured a good connection with relevant developments, opportunities and needs in circles of key stakeholders such as scientists and science journalists. In this way, research results and guidelines were validated by key professionals and practitioners in the field.

This report looks into the contribution of the ESB in 4 crucial project areas: research, resources, teaching/training and policy. The report provides a description of the activities of the ESB members in each of these fields,

1. Introduction

The overall objective of RETHINK has been to provide recommendations and guidelines to maintain and improve the quality of interactions in the new science communication landscape. In addition, RETHINK has aimed to provide support to re-examine and re-orientate science communication across Europe.

In this endeavour, the role of the ESB has been rather crucial, contributing to the 4 areas of the project mentioned above.

1.1 Composition of the ESB

The ESB consists of journalists, scientists, science communication scholars and key stakeholders' representatives (enterprises, gender expert, diversity expert).

Candidates to the ESB were suggested by project partners and approved by the Executive Board, which is the governing body of the consortium for the implementation of the project.

The ESB membership is formalized by a letter of interest (see Annex 2)

The consortium carefully selected the members of the Sounding Board. The selection criteria included:

- their experience in research and project management,
- their prominent role in their respective scientific communities,
- their prominent role in national and international science communication arena, and their link to relevant stakeholders.

The Covid19 Pandemic significantly delayed the working with the ESB, which started in March 2021. However, both the consortium and the ESB members strived to work together and enhance the outcomes of the Rethink project, often going beyond what was initially anticipated.

An overview of the different ESB members is presented in Annex 1.

2. Contribution

The contribution of each of the European Sounding Board Members has been divided into four different areas: Research, resources, training and policy. An extensive presentation of this contribution is offered in the following sections of this report.

2.1 Research

2.1.1 ESB feedback on research conducted

The RETHINK project has produced research findings concerning three different areas:

- the actors, roles, relations and networks in the new science communication landscape;
- the openness and reflexivity of sensemaking practices of individuals and collectives;
- teaching and training of science communication professionals and scientists.

European Sounding Board members have contributed with an evaluation of the research conducted. They focused specifically on bridging the gap between theory and practice and on improving the quality and relevance of the project's research findings.

ESB members reflected upon the presentations by RETHINK researchers and offered feedback. Members commented on a number of issues in relation to Sensemaking:

- How People talk about "trust in science" instead of "trust in government"
- How People's sensemaking practices are so influenced by their context (who they know in their own personal circle or friends and family; their educational background, etc.)
- The fact that science still needs to fight for its place against non-science
- On how surprising is to expect people to trust or understand, while experts, scientists, etc. have created a gap between science and society and now they are expecting it to disappear.
- How difficult and overwhelming finding scientific information can be
- Why the suspicion/distrust of information provided seemed directed towards official organisations

ESB members also discussed the following matters in relation to sensemaking:

- How important it is to conduct research with as many different audiences and communities as possible so that the widest range of views are included
- The role of Design thinking and a more empathic approach to communication

- The science process is not understood by most people outside science - it is presented in school as a set of black and white facts - not a process of investigation seeking to approach 'truth' with many twists and turns on the way - it is often 'expected' to deliver 100% certainty but this is so unfair as the future is uncertain in every other walk of life!
- How the participatory model of science communication has never been more relevant
- There are so many "unaccounted" channels of science communication
- How limited our impact is, if we do not take into consideration personal situation and contexts
- The need for trustful, closed and diverse sources of information
- The importance of emotional aspects in communication, and how it could be deemed more important and utilised in the area.
- the importance of "trusted messengers" in sci-comm of such topics: perceived members of the same community/constituency that can help to address "framing" distrust on some topics. In environmental science, this effect is known to be strong, e.g. "conservative" messengers on climate change achieving greater engagement of otherwise skeptical conservative audiences, etc.

In relation to science communication quality, they also questioned whether:

- Is a more rigid approach to Scicomm somehow self-limiting?
- Digital education helps or hinders participatory science communication

2.1.2 ESB contribution to the Special edition of Journal of Science Communication

Extensive contribution by particular ESB members (M. Achiam and J. Roche were also editors) has been made into RETHINK scientific publications with particular emphasis on the second [JCOM](#) Rethink special edition "Inclusion, reflection and co-creation: responsible scicomm across the globe". The 2nd JCOM Special Edition is a deliverable (D6.5) of WP6 "ENGAGE: Dissemination and Communication". JCOM is a gateway to a vast community of science communication practitioners and researchers and it is coordinated by SML (WP6 Leader).

Science communication continues to develop and change, as a discipline, practice and professional career path, with significant growth in both professional practice and academic study. Changes in the relationships between science and society and its increasing inclusion in official discourses have opened new opportunities for dialogue and collaboration. At the same time, this may have produced challenges for the authority of science, which can be openly contested, negotiated and transformed in public arenas.

This transformation of the relationships between science and society has been fundamentally intensified by the digitalization of the media landscape. New media have increased the diversity of

actors using, sharing and generating science content, their communication practices and the strategies they use. Even though we witness a significant rise in the quantity of science communication circulating in all kinds of media – traditional/ new, mediated/ unmediated, we also acknowledge the major challenges the aforementioned developments pose for science communication. Within this background, RETHINK’s overall objective is to contribute to making the European science communication ecosystem more open, inclusive, reflexive and adaptive.

RETHINK Second Special Issue therefore provides a significant contribution to the project’s overall aim, as it centers on “responsible science communication – challenges for practice”. What does it mean to be a ‘responsible science’ communicator? Are there general criteria used to assess responsible science communication across the globe? What are the commonalities and the differences emerging when defining the characteristics of responsible science communication around the world? What is the contribution of inclusion, reflexivity and co-creation to responsible science communication practices? Can these concepts be considered the pillars of responsible science communication worldwide?

The second JCOM Special Issue titled Responsible Science Communication across the globe consists of papers and commentaries tackling three identified subthemes related to the responsible science communication main theme:

- Responsible science communication = inclusion
- Responsible science communication = reflexivity
- Responsible science communication = co creation

Commentary section: responsible science communication around the globe. Contributions from authors across different geographical regions on what responsible science communication looks like in their context.

The RETHINK project has commissioned all papers and commentaries and expects to publish the Special Issue between May and June 2022.

Articles

Co-design methodological approach for citizen science communication strategies directed to quadruple-helix stakeholders

All authors: Joana Magalhães, Blanca Guasch, Rosa Arias¹, Ana Elorza, Paolo Giardullo, Cristina Luís, Esther Marín-González, Inês Navalhas, Marzia Mazzonetto

The ‘Engagement Incubator’: Using Design to stimulate reflexivity about Public Engagement with Science

All authors: Jo Bailey, Rhian Salmon, Maja Horst

Roles, incentives, training and audiences for science communication: Perspectives from female science communicators

All authors: Wilkinson, C., Milani, E., Ridgway, A., and Weitkamp, E.

Towards the reflective science communication practitioner

All authors: Roedema, T.F.L., Rerimassie, V.G., Broerse, J.E.W, and Kupper, J.F.H

Rethinking science engagement: Re-framing science engagement as a benefit to the individual, rather than a benefit to

All authors: Kerr, Gary and Keith, Lindsay

Commentaries

Responsible science communication in Latin America: reflections on challenges

All authors: Claudia Aguirre, Sergio de Regules

Commentary: ReThinking Iteratively (from Australia)

All authors: Joan Leach

Beyond the needs of science - can openness and reflexivity push the polish science communication further?

All authors: Wiktor Gajewski

'Responsible Science Communication in Africa: Rethinking Drivers of Policy, Afrocentricity and Public Engagement

All authors: Elizabeth Rasekoala

Developing open, reflexive and socially responsible science communication research and practice

All authors: Dr Eric A. Jensen

Table 1: List of Articles & Commentaries in the Second Special JCOM

2.2 Resources

As part of WP3, the project has developed training resources and programs to improve science communication capacities (<https://www.rethinkscicomm.eu/resources/rethink-scicomm-training-navigator/>). The training resources have been developed to address science communication competence levels by focusing on the themes outlined. They include materials for the introduction of

themes and to help to stimulate discussion, reflection and learning, which will seed new ideas. For the latter, quick tools that are applicable within single training sessions, as well as deep dives that need a bit more time and can be applied over more sessions, have been developed.

Tools for introducing themes contain several resources for getting people acquainted with overarching themes of science communication. Quick tools contain a summary of resources that are applicable within a single session of a course. Resources are developed for specific competence levels and themes. Quick tools can be used in combination with every introductory resource and also in combination with deep dives and in a flexible order. Deep dives encompass resources that can be used over the course of two or more sessions up to a whole term. Again, resources are developed for specific competence levels and themes. The work on these single or group activities takes place during or outside of course time. Students report their findings during the training sessions in front of the plenary and/or submit a report. Deep dives can be used in combination with every introductory resource and also in combination with quick tools.

The second meeting with the ESB members was dedicated to a presentation and feedback on these resources.

ESB members had to offer feedback by conducting particular exercises that focused on the following questions. Their evaluation feedback is included in the subsequent points:

1. What are the assets of these resources?

- a. Lots of resources
- b. Impressive coverage of areas, cannot think of an area of sci-comm in the modern world which is not covered
- c. The real-world exemplars developed from interviews are crucial
- d. They cover a lot of different aspects
- e. The framework is clear
- f. References and literature are very useful
- g. Easy to classify and choose and organize
- h. They are clearly designed for different type of audiences and you add a guidance on that which makes them easier to choose
- i. They are supported by data (factsheets)

2. What have we missed? What would you like to see more of or what would you change?

- a. Perhaps some greater clarity on how these resources might be used for training different actors: the needs of researchers as communicators, vs training science communication professionals, are different
- b. Greater focus on the social media/'grassroots' scicomm aspects, which have much bigger reach/influence than is suggested here
- c. Need to consider a wider range of science communication platforms and communicators
- d. How to communicate "boring science"?
- e. They are super textual, which is easy and good, but I lack other type of formats
- f. They seem a little too analogic and not very digital-driven
- g. Provide more examples and prototypes or maybe use some of these resources to co-design prototypes
- h. Present more views from individuals and organisations "on the fringe" - not directly involved in scicomm but actively contributing to it
- i. Use perspectives from outside the scicomm community

3. How could we make them better/more user-friendly?

- a. The pdf with all the resources is rather daunting; it might be better to chunk it up
- b. The "introduction" components (e.g. "short introduction" in manual, and the video to some extent) would benefit from re-structuring to lead with what the resources deliver, in terms of outcomes that are relevant to the target audience of trainers
- c. Most of it is slick, but some things are a bit rough (like the stickman)
- d. Break them down into several small tools inside the big box
- e. Manual for young scientists: make tangible/case studies of tools
- f. Try to convey specific examples, rather than general
- g. Differentiate how you can use resource material for different sources
- h. Design of the "big content" part could be improved by introducing more pictures, tables, infographics etc. Minilectures, prompts and case studies look good
- i. Co-design involving many different expertise

Who could benefit from this type of training?

Please identify in the group up to 5 target groups and write them at the end of the arrows. If there are specific resources relevant to the group, name them please. Discuss how could we reach these target groups. Use post-its.

1. Sci Comm Students
 - a. Possible "recruitment tool" for scicomm industry careers for science students taking a sci-com module
 - b. Highlight the strategic elements of this training to help students to understand the wider context
 - c. How can the sensemaking protocol be used in practice? This could be drawn out for students.
 - d. But there are also fundamentals (e.g. audiences) that will stay the same.
 - e. Highlight for students how the landscape is constantly changing and will continue to do so (you need to be adaptable).
2. Professional Science Communicators
 - a. Nice to have real life examples to spark conversations
 - b. How can the quality framework be applied in this context?
3. Scientists
 - a. Real life exemplars that are hard to engage are helpful.
 - b. Scientists interested in doing sci com, want something ready to use. So they need to be practical as well.
 - c. Generally helpful for people interested in getting into Scicomm
 - d. level of detail and referencing is good for scientists - shows the evidence base in sci com.
4. Science journalists, science demonstrators, the younger population
5. Creators who use social media but also new channels to build their audiences and choose a science beat
6. Students, researchers in humanities and social sciences
7. Interdisciplinary practitioners and researchers

8. Activist groups
9. Local organisations and NGOs
10. SciCom practitioners, as a checkpoint for usual practices and have new resources to explore
11. Editors and journalists in innovative media (not only explainers, rather professionals who explore contexts and connections)
12. Citizen science projects
13. Politicians

How could you disseminate / use these materials?

- Science media centre - they may be useful as they do some training (UK)
- General media? could be worth a press release
- Psci-com network
- NCCPE (UK) also do training - they have a library of resources

2.3 Teaching and Training

The project has benefited from the ESB members feedback on the RETHINK quality framework, quality criteria identified in the project's research and approaches on how to assess and also secure science communication quality. Besides, their input has contributed to the adaptation of training curricula to the developments in the digital communication landscape and related challenges for science communication education. ESB members carried this knowledge in the extensive training events that took place in the final year of project.

2.3.1 Rethink Winter School

ESB members contributed extensively in the preparation and delivery of the Rethink Winter School (Feb 2022).

The RETHINK Winter School 2022 (<https://www.ecsite.eu/activities-and-services/news-and-publications/participate-rethink-science-communication-and>) was organised for early career researchers, journalists, policy-makers, community leaders and all other agents of change who want to learn about communicating science in relation to complex societal issues. The Winter School was a great opportunity for anyone wishing to challenge assumptions, make new connections with underserved audiences, and contribute to an open and trustworthy public conversation about science.

While science communication may be more important than ever, it is also more challenging. We live in a time of uncertainty that challenges established relationships between science, media, publics and politics. Science is openly contested in the public arena by actors that at best raise doubt and at worst

respond antagonistically to scientific practice. Efforts to shift towards a new science communication ecosystem, one that is more adaptive and at the same time reliable and trustworthy, have been at the heart of the RETHINK project. This Winter School focused on and provided tools for practitioners that want to be connectors between various stakeholders and a variety of audiences.

It focused on uncovering the challenging dynamics in the scicomm ecosystem, on the transformation that is needed in the science communication ecosystem, including taking on a sensemaking perspective that allows for insights into the personal situations and social context by which citizens make sense of science (day 1), including roles and repertoires of science communication practitioners (day 2), and by an end-seminar wherein sub-groups present and discuss the ideal and imaginary science communication practice (day 3). In interactive sessions, a group project, and in discussions with expert practitioners, participants in this course develop a reflective practice - with the overarching aim to co-create a scicomm practice looks towards a future in which science becomes more a point of connection than one of polarisation.

Aside from training on particular Rethink concepts, tools, material, etc. there was strong emphasis on three “Meet the Expert” sessions. These were delivered by ESB members. ESB members engaged extensively in both smaller online groups (using the Zoom application’s breakout room function), as well as plenary (online) sessions. The emphasis has been on particular themes, such as understanding audiences (this theme is linked to Rethink’s own underserved audiences strand), the gap between science in the lab and science communication, tips to build successful scicomm networks (Rethinkerspaces hubs) and many more. In these events, ESB members were interviewed by the participants and were also involved in mentoring.

2.3.2 Rethink Workrooms

Over the course of four weekly sessions, RETHINK project brought together two dozen science engagement professionals, four researchers and eight external experts (members of the project’s European Sounding Board) for a theory-practice bridging experiment. United by their quest to find new ways of interacting with audiences, the involved practitioners formed four teams around four real life challenges or “problems”, brought forward as case studies by participants themselves and all relating to engaging new, hard-to-reach or underserved audiences. The teams’ mission: provide peer advice to their “problem owner”, using two specific conceptual tools as a lens and problem-solving lever.

Table 1: Overview of the four-week workshop process

In these events participants worked with sensemaking and roles.

In a few words: "Recent research suggests that scientific knowledge is not self-evident, stable or fixed. Instead, people’s understanding and interpretation of science is influenced by their beliefs and backgrounds. They arrive at different interpretations of science depending on their values, interests, motivations and contexts (...). According to the sensemaking theory, gaps in knowledge are a human condition, which is why knowledge is never complete. People are constantly making sense trying to bridge the gaps in their knowledge as they are moving through time and space. In order to do so, they draw on a variety of sources such as previous experience, expectations, emotions, values and interest.¹"

“What can science engagement as a field learn from sensemaking?” Participants were asked. Many hinted at the importance of context and “understanding where people are coming from”, saying that the concept “incentivize[d] [them] to work on a deeper understanding [of their audiences] than before”. Participants were curious to hear from ESB members how sensemaking might articulate with other concepts widely used in the science engagement community, such as science capital and agency.

While sensemaking focuses on the “demand” side of science communication (how audiences make sense of science), the second concept, roles, helps rethink the “supply” side of science communication, i.e. the practices of science communicators. As part of their research, UWE looked at

¹ *Opportunities and barriers for strengthening the quality of interaction between science and society*, RETHINK project deliverable 5.1, May 2021, p.7.

the roles adopted by science communication professionals with the aim of forming different types of connections with audiences, and identified six of them: the broker, the listener, the includer, the enabler, the educator, the entertainer.

When stepping back at the end of the process and listing what the concept of roles can bring to science engagement as a field, participants stated that it helped them see their own skills and postures and those of other colleagues more explicitly, also potentially identifying gaps in their team's composition. They also said that it could be used as a "checklist" when working on projects, making sure that different perspectives were taken into account.

Finally, an ESB member (Dr Joseph Roche) conducted a small survey in the final session. Here are its findings:

Throughout the RETHINK Workrooms, 6 activities were held with 15 participants who took part in this feedback report by answering some questions and giving their opinion.

Firstly, the concept of sensemaking was addressed and what it could mean in the context of science communication. According to participants, the term of sensemaking in science communication is related to understand the process of creating and how it can have an effect on communicating science. It is using reason and feelings to give meaning to experiences, find our own place among others and makes science communication aligned with interests of the public. It's a micromoment before the actual communication action when you grasp a new concept or idea to understand the different points of view crashing in one topic. It helps us question how do the experiences and knowledge a person has affected the way she interprets science and thus helps to connect with other people and try to suit the best of communication for them.

This concept, as well as the concept of different scicomm roles², are relevant for the participants and in their view, these are the most likely to be shared around them.

Secondly, the atmosphere of the workrooms was discussed, asking participants to describe their impressions and perceptions. Some of them mentioned feeling inspired, engaged, or being in a collaborative and professional form of working. Indeed, the theory-practice bridge and the people from all over Europe and their complementary experiences made it distinctive.

² Milani, E. et al (n.d.). *Reaching underserved audiences - rethink #scicomm*. Retrieved March 20, 2022, from https://www.rethinkscicomm.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/04/RETHINK_Derivable_D1.4_V11_FINAL-1.pdf

From a different perspective, other attendees found the sessions too long and the pace to be fast, suggesting more time to think about solutions, to be more attentive to the break time and have a facilitator for each team, making it easier to interact.

Overall, the Rethink workrooms were successful as participants found them very well prepared and organised with inspiring people from many different places to share some fresh ideas and collaborate with. The format used was very useful, mentioning that it would be gladly used for other projects.

2.4 Policy

ESB members have supported the project, contributing to its policy impact. Their input was crucial to reflect on how the project's outputs and research findings can be shaped into policy recommendations. Besides the project benefited from the members support to further policy impact. ESB members were asked to suggest the use of the resources, disseminate results and use the different outcomes of the project to improve their own theory, add value to their practice and foster institutional change.

ESB members contributed to the Final Policy event organised on the 21st and the 22nd of March 2022. <https://www.ecsite.eu/activities-and-services/news-and-publications/join-final-policy-conference-rethink-tresca-projects>. In Particular 3 ESB members participated in the Panels “Forging connections with new audiences in times of polarisation and misinformation” and “Transformation and reflection: how can reflective practice help us adapt to current complexities?” on both days, as well as in the subsequent discussions

The final conference highlighted ongoing conversations between scientists, policy makers, media and science communication practitioners and a variety of publics. The conference focused on how we can strengthen the connections between various stakeholders and publics in order to more effectively respond to current and future uncertainties. We look towards a future in which science becomes more a point of connection than one of polarisation. In a series of keynotes, panels, and engaging conversations in which ESB members contributed, we discussed and co-created how science communication as a practice can build towards public trust - by making new connections and shaping the conversations that matter.

Conclusion

Despite the challenge of the Covid19 pandemic, the role and contribution of the ESB in the Rethink project has been rather successful. ESB members, with their wealth of expertise and backgrounds, were able to engage in many aspects of the project, namely its research, resources, training and policy events. The entire exercise demonstrates the important and innovative role that such Sounding Boards can play in EU-funded projects, as they offer the opportunity to consortia to reach beyond its own expertise to actors that are leaders in their field. They also offer project audiences and target groups opportunities to meet and work closely with these actors in a variety of learning settings.

Annex 1: Bios of ESB members

Marianne Achiam

Marianne is an associate professor at the University of Copenhagen, Denmark. Her research is about how the science of scientists is transformed and presented in education and communication initiatives, and how it finally becomes the science of learners. I was part of the Hypatia project (2015-2018), where the project partners worked to make science communication activities gender-inclusive in institutions across Europe. Her focus, both in research and in teaching, is on sustainability and how science communication can be shaped to support a sustainable future.

Andrea Bandelli

Andrea is the Executive Director and “diplomat in chief” of SGI, where he manages the relationships with all network members and external stakeholders. A keen listener and an experienced speaker, Andrea is responsible for developing and implementing the network culture of Science Gallery. A world citizen by trade, Andrea’s academic background includes a MA in Economics, a master in Science Communication and a PhD in Social Sciences, with a specialisation in scientific citizenship. Andrea is a member of the Expert Network of the World Economic Forum and has been a Cultural Leader in Davos in 2017 and 2018, and in Dalian in 2017 and 2019. He is a member of the board of the Deutsches Museum in Munich.

Dean Burnett

Dr Dean Burnett is a neuroscientist and author. Having completed his undergraduate and postgraduate degrees in neuroscience at Cardiff University, he spent many years lecturing for a psychiatry programme while contributing scientific articles and commentary to the Guardian website. He is now a full time author and speaker, with his bestselling science books about the brain having been translated into over 30 languages.

Barbara Capone

Barbara is an Assistant Professor in the field of Theoretical Physics and Nanomaterials. Part of her research is dedicated to the development of materials for water sanitation to be sustainably developed in developing countries with local resources. Since 2012 she is co-founder and CEO of Sunshine4Palestine, a charity that operates in Palestine. The NGO, in collaboration with Bethlehem University, the European Physical Society and ICTP (Unesco), started in 2015 Science4People, a science dissemination project in Palestine aimed at sensitising kids/young students on the theme of science through a ludic approach.

Jon Copley

Dr Jon Copley is Associate Professor of Ocean Exploration & Public Engagement at the University of Southampton, UK, and co-founder and Director of SciConnect Ltd, a capacity-building company that has trained more than 15,000 scientists to share their work with wider audiences, for clients including research institutions, funding bodies, government agencies, NGOs and companies across the UK and in Europe. Jon is also a “popular science” writer, former Reporter and Assistant News Editor of New Scientist magazine, and science advisor for broadcast series such as BBC Blue Planet II. For further information, please see www.joncopley.com.

Mart Loog

Mart Loog is a professor of molecular systems biology at the Institute of Technology, University of Tartu. Mart received his Ph.D. in medicinal biochemistry from Uppsala University, Sweden, in 2002, followed by postdoctoral training at the University of California, San Francisco (UCSF). In 2006, Mart established his independent laboratory at the newly established Institute of Technology. Recently, he established a Core Laboratory for Wood Chemistry and Bioprocessing that aims to provide services for industry and also forms a consortium of research labs focusing on the chemical and biotechnological valorization of wood industry waste streams (www.woodbiotech.com)

Vanessa Mignan

Vanessa Mignan is an independent trainer and social inclusion consultant for science engagement institutions. In the past ten years, she has developed, implemented and evaluated educational and training programmes on science engagement, creativity and social justice at both national and European levels. She loves mixing different people and approaches in order to create inclusive spaces for novel encounters with knowledge.

Chris Rapley

Professor Chris Rapley CBE is Professor of Climate Science at University College London (UCL). He is a Fellow of UCL and of St Edmund's College Cambridge, a member of the Academia Europaea, Chair of the European Science Foundation's European Space Sciences Committee, Member of the Advisory Board of the UK government's Clean Growth Fund, Patron of the Surrey Climate Commission, a member of the UK Science Museum Group's Science Advisory Board, a member of the Science Advisory board of Scientists' Warning, and a member of the UK Parliamentary and Scientific Committee. More recently he has focused on the role of climate scientists in delivering value to society through decision making, public policy and more effective communication.

Joseph Roche

Dr Joseph Roche is an astrophysicist and assistant professor in science education at Trinity College Dublin. He leads the Science & Society research group and teaches modules on "Science Education, Communication, and Society" at undergraduate, masters, and doctoral level. He is the PhD programme coordinator at the School of Education. His research interests include: informal science education, citizen science, science communication, public engagement in science, and higher education science.

Elisabetta Tola

Elisabetta has a Ph.D. in Microbiology. She is science and data journalist. She was a Tow-Knight fellow 2019 for entrepreneurial journalism at the Craig Newmark Graduate School of Journalism, New York. She is a co-founder of the Italian science communication agency [formicablu](http://formicablu.com) and a founder of Facta.eu, a non profit project bringing the scientific methodology into journalism. She is a managing editor at [Il Bo Live](http://IlBoLive.com), the online cultural magazine edited by the University of Padua, radio presenter at [Radio3scienza](http://Radio3scienza.com), RAI Radio3, the Italian national public radio. She co-authors international multimedia and data journalism projects, like Seedversity.org and [SEEDcontrol](http://SEEDcontrol.com). She is also media trainer and lecturer on digital and data science journalism at different Masters and journalism schools.

Annex 2: Letter of Interest

A Letter of Interest

To be adapted by each member of the ESB (for new members)

[Date]

[ESB member full name]

Letter of interest

Dear RETHINK coordinator,

With this letter, [ESB member full name] signifies that it is aware of the project RETHINK with project ID 824573

[ESB member full name] submits this expression of interest to participate in the RETHINK Project European Sounding Board, contributing to:

- Provide input and feedback to the RETHINK research outcomes;
- Ensure that the recommendations and guidelines the project produces are relevant and applicable to the all different stakeholder groups.

[Signature here]

Name of the European Sounding Board member

Annex 3: Contribution ESB members

ESB members dedicated six days to the Rethink project. Here is an overview of how each of them has contributed to the various Rethink activities (Research, Resources, Training, Policy)

	Research	Resources	Training	Policy
Andrea Bandelli				
Barbara Capone				
Chris Rapley				
Dean Burnett				
Elisabetta Tola				
Jon Copley				
Joseph Roche				
Marianne Achiam				
Mart Loog				
Vanessa Mignan				